
Research

Green Harmony: Global and Regional Dynamics for SDG-2030

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Abstract: The achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 hinges on the intricate interplay between environmental performance and human development. This study employs Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) on both a global scale and within the context of South Asia, utilizing the latest Environmental Performance Index (EPI) and Human Development Index (HDI) reports from 2022. Globally, the CCA underscores that Environmental Performance significantly influences key SDGs, with metrics explaining nearly 85% of variations in Life Expectancy (SDG-3) and Per Capita Gross National Income (SDG-8.5). Education indicators, such as Expected Years of Schooling (SDG-4.3) and Mean Years of Schooling (SDG-4.4), are strongly influenced by Environmental Health, showcasing a profound connection. Interestingly, the Human Development Index demonstrates a robust correlation (92.8%) with Environmental Health but displays a less pronounced relationship (48.2%) with Ecosystem Vitality on a global scale. The findings unveil a global synergy, with composite indices exhibiting strong correlation (86%) and mutual explanatory power. However, the South Asia regional analysis presents a divergent narrative, revealing statistically insignificant insights and negative influences on environmental performance (-4.6%) and human development (-20.3%) through ecosystem vitality and mean years of schooling, respectively. This research contributes valuable insights for global progress towards SDG-2030, emphasizing the need for tailored attention and policy implementation in South Asia to attain sustainable development. The implications inform policymakers and stakeholders, advocating for integrated policies that empower education, foster inclusive economic growth, nurture health and environment synergy, bolster ecosystem resilience, and promote data-driven decision-making. Employing Canonical Correlation Analysis through statistical tools such as E-views 12, SPSS 25 and Stata 15, this study underscores the significance of fostering a harmonious relationship between nature and human development for long-term societal benefits.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), Environmental Performance, Human Development, Global and South Asia.

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Introduction

Sustainable development links human and environmental development. Environmental performance is how well society and economies manage and reduce their environmental impacts while fostering sustainability (Steinhäuser et al 2022). It involves practices that decrease pollution, save resources, mitigate climate change, protect ecosystems, and promote sustainability. Sustainable growth requires good environmental performance to preserve natural resources, ecosystems, biodiversity, and the environment (Avnimelech, Y. 2009). Human development addresses education, health, income, and social inclusion to improve individuals and communities. Sustainable development improves human well-being and quality of life while protecting natural resources and ecosystems (Hermwille et al 2017). Environmental performance and human development are linked, therefore sustainable development necessitates managing their synergies and trade-offs. Policymakers may support sustainable development that improves environmental performance and human well-being by integrating environmental and social factors (Sterling et al 2017). Environmental performance improves resource sustainability, ecosystem protection, and risk reduction (Avnimelech, Y. 2009). Promoting human development guarantees that people and communities have access to critical services, better living situations, and advancement possibilities.

Background of the research

According to the Sustainable growth Goals-2030 (Boluk et al 2019) (SDGs-2030), environmental risk management is crucial to human growth (Steinhäuser et al 2022). Human advancement and environmental risk management support sustainable development goals. Natural catastrophes, pollution, deforestation, and other environmental hazards endanger human health and safety (Avnimelech, Y. 2009). Sustainable environmental risk management can reduce poverty by producing jobs, promoting sustainable livelihoods, and ensuring equitable resource access (Hermwille et al 2017). Environmental issues threaten agriculture, tourism, and infrastructure, threatening economic growth. Environmental risk management in economic planning supports resilience, sustainability, and long-term growth. One of the biggest environmental threats is climate change (Avnimelech, Y. 2009). For SDG-2030, environmental risk management and human development must be linked (Steinhäuser et al 2022). We can protect human well-being alleviate poverty, promote sustainable economic growth, reduce climate change, conserve ecosystem services, and create collaboration by controlling environmental risks. Building a sustainable future where people and the world thrive requires this connection.

To evaluate environmental management on a global scale, the Centre for Environmental Law and Policy at Yale University established an EPI in 2006 (Zuo et al 2017). To Emerson et al. (2010), "specific expression that provides information about the environmental performance of an organization" is what an environmental performance index is defined as according to ISO 14064. EPI offers policymakers a more accessible framework for evaluating international comparison performance; it is a result-oriented quantitative indicator that is more sophisticated (Popescu et al 2017). With the help of the Environmental Performance Index, we can see which nations are doing the most to improve the environment and which ones are lagging behind (Liu et al 2017).

Environmental management literature can be organized into three main areas (Huang et al 2020). First, researchers assessed the environmental sustainability of chosen cities, regions, and sectors (Samuel et al 2019; Jang et al 2019). Second, related study considers weights for adding environmental performance. Authors estimated aggregate weights using factor analysis and principal component analysis (Booyesen, F. 2002). Third, scholars are studying environmental factors, most notably money (Opoku et al 2019; Yildiz et al 2017). Economic development reflects all aspects of human development (Hsu et al 2016). As a result, some studies have expanded their focus from the environment-economy relationship to encompass environmental management and human progress. The United Nations Development

Program created the human development index (HDI) in 1990 (UNDP-HDRO report 2016), which is now the most widely used indicator of progress. UNDP periodically publishes HDI rankings and descriptive statistics to depict global GDP and social development worldwide (UNDP-HDRO report 2014).

When per capita income is below US \$1,000, environmental degradation (including resource depletion and pollution) is at its worst, according to Panayiotou's research (1993). According to Shafik (1994), nations with a per capita income of \$12,240 or more enjoy a 2% drop in sulfur dioxide concentration for every 1% increase in that income. In the range of \$3,000 to \$12,502 per capita GDP, Kaufmann found an inverse relationship between sulfur dioxide concentration and GDP (Kaufmann et al 1998). Specifically, concentrations of sulfur dioxide increased and decreased in relation to GDP per capita. Orlitzky et al. (2011) found a positive correlation between financial/economic success and environmental sustainability, which means that being environmentally sustainable could be a competitive advantage if financial/economic performance were to improve. A stronger economy is indicated by higher Human Development Index and Economic Performance Index scores (Liu et al 2017). In most cases, the research found a positive correlation between environmental management and progress in human development.

Environmental Performance: Environmental performance measures and evaluates an entity's environmental impact. It evaluates how successfully a person, organization, or system reduces its environmental impact. Environmental performance can be assessed at the individual, business, and national levels. "Blueprint for a Green Economy" incorporated environmental consequences while making economic decisions for the first time (Pearce, D 1989). The study of environmental performance has grown from individual firms to industries to national and regional governments. (Thoresen, J. 1999) suggested adding global environmental impacts to the environmental performance index. This study examines the meaning, implementation, and evaluation of environmental performance across nations. The "Performance Monitoring Indicators Handbook" by (Mosse, R.; Sontheimer, L.E. 1996) introduced environmental performance indicators (EPIs) and their impact on World Bank operations.

The Environmental Sustainability Index (ESI) was created and published from 2002 to 2005 for these reasons. Besides economics, the environmental sustainability index covers environmental and social variables (Esty et al 2005). In 2006, moderate measures were recommended by the World Economic Forum, the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, the Centre for International Earth Science Information Network at Columbia University, and the Centre for Environmental Law and Policy at Yale University (Esty et al 2006). An environmental performance index (EPI) that would be administered on a worldwide scale twice a year was advised upon. In comparison to the more complex and goal-oriented Environmental Sustainability Index, the Environmental Performance Index provides a more accurate picture of environmental effect. In order to assess progress in light of new environmental issues, indicators are refined to include the best proxy, generated from reliable data sources and rigorous techniques. Composite indices must incorporate data standardization, aggregation, weighting, and performance assessment beyond indicators and nations (Esty et al 2006).

Most of this environmental performance index design follows EPI's guidelines, which provides four standards for indicator selection: Credible data is (1) adaptable to a variety of situations related to a country's environment, (2) usable in evaluating performance, (3) produced from open, verifiable sources and procedures that establish a starting point and allow for subsequent monitoring, and (4) high-quality. Health and environmental vitality comprise EPI. Since 2006, when only 133 countries (Esty et al 2006) had clearly defined environmental dimensions, the number has steadily increased to 149 in 2008, 163 in 2010, and 132 in 2012 as data availability has improved and the number of countries with environmental performance targets has grown. 180 participated in 2016 and 2022, up from 178 in 2014 (Hsu et al 2014). Every two years, data was used to fine-tune the index's environmental performance measures. In 2006, the

Environmental Performance Index (EPI) took sixteen indicators into account, including child mortality, indoor air pollution, water, sanitation, nitrogen loading, urban particulates, regional ozone, water consumption, conservation of wilderness, preservation of ecoregions, rate of timber harvest, agricultural subsidies, overfishing, energy efficiency, renewable energy, and others (EPI 2006). In 2008, there was an increase to the number of indicators in the Environmental Performance Index (EPI) from 16 to 25, which allowed for more comprehensive reporting on a wide range of topics, including but not limited to: water and sanitation access, indoor air pollution, sulfur dioxide emissions, water quality, water stress, conservation risk, effective conservation, protection of critical habitats, marine protected areas, and more.

Some academics have shown a favorable association between similar environmental performance measurements within the same framework. (Rapport, D.J., 1998) said the dynamic ecological system objective can deliver ecosystem services like clean water and air. According to Jerry (2001), a healthy ecosystem includes natural and man-made elements. Total environmental health is inherent in ecosystem vitality theory, the findings show. Ecosystem vitality affects environmental health because human and society health are linked. According to Zhang et al (2006), ecosystem and environmental health's interconnectedness and interrelationship are indicated by keeping humans healthy, using resources efficiently, and providing environmental quality adequate for human survival. According to (Wicklum et al 1995), ecosystem vitality is a fallacy because it has nothing to do with health and cannot be supported by ecological theory or proved to be related.

The world's nations vowed in the 2022 Glasgow Climate Pact to implement stricter climate policies in order to achieve zero net emissions of greenhouse gases by the middle of the century. The 2022 EPI will help achieve these objectives by include a metric to monitor the degree to which countries have reduced their emissions to zero by the year 2050. Recent data shows that just two countries—the United Kingdom and Denmark—are on track to achieve greenhouse gas neutrality by the year 2050. Indicators of plastic contamination in the ocean and recycling rates are increasingly part of waste management. In order to acknowledge the significance of agriculture to society's health, the 2022 EPI incorporates a trial indicator on sustainable pesticide use. The most extensive worldwide environmental study to date, the 2022 EPI, uses forty performance indicators spread over eleven problem categories. Policy objectives derived from these subject areas include promoting ecological vitality, addressing climate change, and protecting the environment. The EPI group transforms raw environmental data into indicators that rank nations from worst to best on a scale from zero to one hundred in order to make EPI assessments widely available. There are 180 nations that will be examined in EPI 2022.

Human Development as Sustainable Development Goals (SDG-2030): A country's overall human development can be seen by looking at its Human Development Index (HDI). In order to compare the level of happiness and quality of life among nations, the UNDP created this index (Glatzer, W. 2011). Health, education, and income are included in the HDI variables. First, the SDG-3 birth rate: This metric shows the average longevity of a baby. It's a way to gauge the well-being and contentment of a community. A child's expected years of education (SDG-4.3) is an estimate of the number of years a kid of school entrance age would receive, while the mean years of education (SDG-4.4) is the average number of years individuals aged 25 and older receive; these two indicators comprise the education component of the HDI. Gross National Product per capita (SDG-8.5): Gross National Product per capita is a measure of a country's level of life that includes average income. In a study conducted in 1990, the UNDP pushed for the HDI. Choice is one of the most important aspects of human development, according to a 2000 research by the UNDP and the HDRO. Every person should be able to make their own decisions in life as a result of human progress (UNDP-HDRO report 2004). In order to eliminate obstacles to people's physical health, literacy, and political freedom, and resource scarcity, HDI measurements should be revised, according to Nobel winner in economics Amartya Sen (Sen, A. 2005). (Haq, M.U. 1995) argued that economic development plans should put the well-being of citizens ahead of GDP in reaction to the

1990 human development index report. One of the problems with GNI is that it fails to take human flourishing into account when calculating HDI.

Human Development Index (HDI) rankings nations and areas based on their level of human development. Unlike the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), which takes into account four representative indicators gross national income, life expectancy at birth, projected years of schooling, and mean years of schooling. As a result of being too preoccupied with numbers, the HDI has neglected its human roots (Ogwang, T. 1994). To more accurately reflect people's development, Hicks proposed adjusting HDI weights (Hicks, D. A. 1997). According to (Sagar et al 1998), the HDI report has remained mostly unchanged over the years because it has been reformulated so many times. Although the HDI may place too much emphasis on economic concerns, Hopkins discovered that the three dimensions of human development can be used together as a composite measure of living standards (Hopkins, M. 1991). Various nations have different challenges at different stages of development, as pointed out by Noorbakhsh (2002). This means that poor countries need an HDI that is specific to their situation. Factor analysis weights were used by Noorbakhsh (2002) to construct the Human Development Index. Lai posits that the HDI's cross-sectional and longitudinal significance could be enhanced by employing principal component analysis in (Lai, D. 2000).

The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) came up with the Human Development Index (HDI) to measure "average achievement in three basic dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living." The HDI has been released every year since 1990, with the exception of 2012–2020. Even though the HDI was on the rise overall, over 90% of the 191 countries tracked in 2022 had a decline from 2020 to 2022. As a result of COVID-19, these declines occurred. The HDI indicator gives a score between 0 and 1, with 1 being the maximum possible score, signifying the level of human potential. High (0.7-0.79), medium (0.55-0.70), low (0.55), and extremely high (0.8-1.0) are the four extremes of the HDI scale. "Low human development" describes nations whose HDIs are lower than 0.55. Least developed countries (LDCs) suffer from educational opportunities, poverty, healthcare, and inept leadership. A "new uncertainty complex," as outlined in the HDI report for 2022, has emerged as a result of the world's most pressing environmental crises, the rapid acceleration of societal industrialization (including the rise in automation), and the widening gap between the political and social classes. This new uncertainty complex is illustrated by the research using the COVID-19 pandemic and the 2022 Ukraine war.

Environmental Performance and Human Development: The link between environmental performance and human growth is complicated. Human development is the well-being and advancement of individuals and communities, while environmental performance is the sustainability and environmental impact of human activities. A holistic and integrated approach is needed to improve environmental performance and human development. It requires sustainable practices, renewable energy, biodiversity conservation, waste management, and environmental concerns in development planning. Empowering communities, promoting education and awareness, and cooperating internationally are essential for sustainable human growth and environmental protection.

The effects of growing economies on environmental degradation were studied by Panayotou (1993). Per capita incomes below \$1,000 were associated with the greatest rates of resource exhaustion and pollution, according to the study. Increasing incomes causes more people to work to reduce pollution, according to an empirical study that used a huge number of national samples over a lengthy period of time to examine the relationship between economic growth and environmental performance. Water and sanitation are prioritized due to their low cost, and in order to decrease environmental deterioration, most countries require environmental regulations and investments. According to these studies, a robust economy lessens negative effects on the environment. The HDI has a strong correlation with health status, according to principal component analysis (Bloom et al 2003). Expanding the economy, according to Orlitzky et

al. (2011), would improve environmental sustainability. After looking at 149 samples from different nations across several categories, Gallego et al. (2014) found that economic development, education, and institutional factors were essential in determining national environmental performance. Sulfur dioxide emissions are lower in industrialized nations with high per capita GDP, according to Kaufman (Kaufmann et al. 1998). Sammi et al. (2011) used data collected from all countries between 2006 and 2010 to determine the correlation between human development and environmental performance. The industrialized world and other high-HDI countries put a lot of money into environmental protection, but emerging nations and others low-HDI countries don't. Similarly, the findings of Kammi (2011) and Kaufmann (1998) hold true. There is a clear need for additional research into the link between human development and environmental performance, since previous studies have either shown beneficial or insignificant results.

Research Gap, Objectives and Purpose of the Research

Environmental Sustainability, Sustainable development all are essential for human being's current needs and survive. There are some specific sustainable development goals and targets for human development and also have strong and important interconnection between human development issues with environment. Sequential research is very essential to find out up to date interconnections and impacts of environmental indicators and human development indicators for policy development to obtain Sustainable development for Global and South Asia regional perspectives. With this context in mind, we present the following questions for further study. Is environmental performance related to human progress favorably or negatively? How do birthrate, projected years of schooling, mean years of schooling, and gross national product (GNI) relate to environmental performance (ecosystem health and vitality)? What weights do you believe would be most useful when combining the EPI and HDI? Can we establish connections between environmental performance indicators and measures of human development? And how much way does each HDI sub factor have on different indicators of environmental performance?

Primary Objectives and Purpose of the Research is analyze Interrelationships between environmental performance and Human Development as sustainable development Goals (SDG-2030) in the Globe and South Asia regional. The sub objectives of the research also include: (1) Relationship of Life Expectancy at birth (SDG-3), Expected Years of Schooling (SDG-4.3), Mean Years of Schooling (SDG-4.4) and Per Capita Gross National Income (SDG-8.5) with Environmental Performance and Ecosystem Vitality. (2) Measure the appropriate weighs in combining Environmental Performance Index and Human Development Index. (3) Find out Cross-Correlations between Environmental Performance indicators and Human Development Indicators. (4) Analyze the effect of each Human Development sub factor on different indicators of Environmental Performance.

Research Methodology

This research aims to explore the complex dynamics and interdependencies between Environmental Performance and Human development as sustainable development goal (SDG-230) with Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA). Canonical Correlation Analysis will be employed to identify the correlations and interrelationships between environmental performance indicators and Human development indicators as sustainable development goal (SDG-2030) within those two set of variables. H. Hotelling first developed the Canonical Correlation method in the year 1935 (Hotelling, H 1936), but it was not widely used until computers with statistical software. The goal of canonical correlation analysis is to identify the most effective linear combinations of independent and dependent variables (Hsing, T et al 2015). There are two sets of variables in the data, which we will refer to as $\mathbf{X} \in R^{n \times p_1}$ and $\mathbf{Y} \in R^{n \times p_2}$ for a sample size of n . The goal is to identify a set of linear combinations of $\mathbf{X}$ variables denoted as $\mathbf{x}_u = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{u}$, and a set of linear combinations of $\mathbf{Y}$ variables denoted as $\mathbf{y}_v = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{v}$ that maximizes the correlation between the

two sets. Where $u \in R^{p_1}$ and $v \in R^{p_2}$. As the first canonical pair, (x_u, y_v) enjoys special status. Therefore, CCA's ultimate goal is

$$\max_{u,v} \text{corr}(x_u, y_v).$$

If we assume that X and Y are both centered, we may express the objective function as

$$\max_{u,v} \frac{\text{cov}(x_u, y_v)}{[\text{var}(x_u)\text{var}(y_v)]^{-1/2}} = \frac{u^T X^T Y v}{\sqrt{u^T X^T X u v^T Y^T Y v}}. \tag{1}$$

To ensure the solutions are unique, optimization problem can be formulated as

$$\max_{u,v} (u^T S_{X^T Y} v), \text{subject to } u^T S_{X^T X} u = v^T S_{Y^T Y} v = 1,$$

where $S_{X^T Y} = n^{-1} X^T Y$, $S_{X^T X} = n^{-1} X^T X$, $S_{Y^T Y} = n^{-1} Y^T Y$.

Let $\tilde{u} = S_{X^T X}^{-1/2} u$ and $\tilde{v} = S_{Y^T Y}^{-1/2} v$, then we may obtain

$$\max_{u,v} (\tilde{u}^T Q \tilde{v}), \text{subject to } \tilde{u}^T \tilde{u} = 1 \text{ and } \tilde{v}^T \tilde{v} = 1,$$

where $Q = S_{X^T X}^{-1/2} S_{X^T Y} S_{Y^T Y}^{-1/2}$.

The maximum obtained when $\tilde{u}$ and $\tilde{v}$ is respectively the first left and right singular vectors of Q as defined in the SVD (Singular Value Decomposition) of Q .

Extending to multiple canonical pair (u_i, v_i) , $i = 1, \dots, p$, where $p = \min(p_1, p_2)$, denote them in the matrix form as $U, V \in R^{n \times p}$, whose column are u_i 's and v_i 's respectively. The solution is, with the same logic,

$$(U, V) = (S_{X^T X}^{-1/2} \tilde{U}, S_{Y^T Y}^{-1/2} \tilde{V}),$$

where $\tilde{U}$'s and $\tilde{V}$'s columns are respectively the first p left and right singular vectors of Q .

The data can be viewed using just the first few canonical pairs most of the time. Thus, CCA can be seen as an alternative method of achieving dimension reduction.

Data, Data Sources and Variables: In this research, the Human Development Index (HDI) and Environmental Performance Index (EPI) for the year 2022 take center stage. The HDI calculations involve birth rates, projected and mean schooling years, and Gross National Income (GNI) for a comprehensive evaluation of human development across 195 countries and regions. Meanwhile, the EPI dives into ecological vitality and environmental health, amalgamating data from 180 diverse nations. Notably, our study exclusively focuses on the 178 countries and regions equipped with complete data. Harnessing data from reputable sources such as the World Bank, Human Development Index (HDI-2022), and Environmental Performance Index (EPI-2022). Variables are given below in the table.

Dependent Variables (Environmental Performance Index; EPI-2022)	Independent Variables (Human Development Performance Index; HDI -2022)
Environmental Health	Life Expectancy at Birth (Year)
Ecosystem Vitality	Expected Years of Schooling (Year)
	Mean Years of Schooling (Year)
	Per Capita Gross National Income (GNI) in USD

Empirical Analysis and Results

Both the Human Development Variables (with four variables) and Environmental Performance related Variables (with two variables) undergo Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA). Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics for these six variables.

Variables	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Kurtosis	Obs.
Environmental Health	44.83	44.30	12.80	14.60	73.90	2.40	178
Ecosystem Vitality	42.60	39.15	21.49	10.90	94.70	2.66	178
Expected Years of Schooling	13.60	13.56	2.88	6.96	21.05	2.68	178
Gross National Income	19315	12159	19670	731	90918	4.61	178
Life Expectancy at Birth	71.17	71.61	7.53	52.53	84.78	2.40	178
Mean Years of Schooling	8.96	9.26	3.18	2.11	14.09	2.02	178

Table-1: Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 displays the results and test of the canonical correlation analysis. The first set of computed canonical variate pairings has an eigenvalue of 6.161 and a canonical correlation coefficient of 0.928, as shown in Table 2. The canonical correlation coefficient for the second set is 0.306, and the corresponding eigenvalue is 0.103. Since the eigenvalue of the first set of anticipated canonical variates is greater than 1, it is evident that only these two variables adequately explain the data.

Canonical Correlation	R-Squared Canonical Correlation	Null Hypothesis (H0) = Canonical Correlations in the current and following rows are Zero (0).						
		Eigen Value	Wilks Statistic	F Value	Num DF	Den DF	Sign. (P)	
1	0.928	0.8612	6.161	0.127	77.856	8	344	0.000
2	0.306	0.1102	0.103	0.907	5.947	3	173	0.001

Multivariate test and F value approximation

Multivariate test	Statistic	Num DF	Den DF	F Value	Prob > F
Wilk's Lamda	0.12659	8	344	77.8561	0.0000 e
Pillai's Trace	0.953846	8	346	39.4338	0.0000 a
Hotelling-Lawley Trace	6.2641	8	342	133.8952	0.0000 a
Roy's Largest Root	6.16097	4	173	266.4618	0.0000 u

Here, e = exact, a = approximate, u = upper bound of F

Table-2: Canonical Correlation Analysis and test

Wilks' lambda, Pillai's trace, Hotelling-Lawley trace, Roy's greatest root, probability ratio, and approximate F value are all statistically significant at the 0.000 level, demonstrating that the Environmental Performance Index (EPI) canonical variable from the first set is significantly correlated with the Human Development Index (HDI) canonical variable from the second set. The second set's canonical variate pair similarly shows statistical significance, with a p-value of 0.001 for the correlation test. When comparing the two sets of variate pairs, the first set is more significant and robust.

According to the eigenvalues, one of the canonical variables in the first canonical variate pair can account for as much as 98.4% of the variance and information content of the second canonical variable in the same set. Adding the second

canonical variate pair does not help to improve the remaining 1.6% of the reported variation. This is why we restrict our interpretation and analysis to the first canonical pair of variates. As we can see from the above, there is a strong relationship between the EPI and HDI canonical variables and a considerable degree of mutual explanatory power between these two measures.

Variables	Expected Years of Schooling	Gross National Income	Life Expectancy at Birth	Mean Years of Schooling
Expected Years of Schooling	1	0.6986	0.7929	0.7867
Gross National Income	0.6986	1	0.7533	0.6850
Life Expectancy at Birth	0.7929	0.7533	1	0.7437
Mean Years of Schooling	0.7867	0.6850	0.7437	1

Table-3: Human development indicators internal correlation coefficients

Table 3 shows that the linear correlation between the four standard indicators of human development (Expected years of schooling, Mean years of schooling, Gross National Income, and Life expectancy at birth) is more than or very close to 0.7. The mean years of schooling within a country's GNI is 0.6850, making the two numbers somewhat less than or equal to 0.7. As a result, moderate to considerable positive correlations exist between the four indicators of human development in all nations. As a result, raising the bar on any one measure of human development index raises the bar on the other three as well.

Variables	Environmental Health	Ecosystem Vitality
Environmental Health	1	0.5150
Ecosystem Vitality	0.5150	1

Table-4: Environmental Performance indicators internal correlation coefficient

In Table 4, we can see that environmental health and ecosystem vitality have a moderately positive internal correlation (0.5150), with a correlation coefficient of around 0.5 indicating that the two are positively correlated. In the table 5, there is a strong positive link between environmental health and birth life expectancy, expected years of schooling, Gross National Income (GNI) and the mean years of schooling of HDI. However, the positive association with in Human development index and ecosystem vitality was quite moderate, coming in at close to 0.4.

Variables	Environmental Health	Ecosystem Vitality
Expected Years of Schooling	0.8144	0.4169
Gross National Income	0.8496	0.5047
Life Expectancy at Birth	0.8652	0.3675
Mean Years of Schooling	0.7650	0.4745

Table-5: Environmental and Human development indicators inter-coefficient

There is a moderate and positive relationship between ecological vitality and the HDI metrics. The correlation coefficients of HDI with in environmental health are all around 0.8 (Table-5). So, improved of environmental

performance is directly related to human growth. It appears that human progress has a stronger correlation with environmental health than ecological vitality. The estimated canonical coefficients used to characterize the distribution of the canonical variables are shown in Figure 1 and Table 6. As a result, Global measurement of the canonical variables of the first canonical variate pair can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Environmental Performance} = 0.997 \times \text{The Environmental Health} + 0.007 \times \text{The Ecosystem Vitality}.$$

$$\text{Human development} = 0.383 \times \text{The Life expectancy at birth} + 0.215 \times \text{The Expected years of schooling} + 0.083 \times \text{The Mean years of schooling} + 0.421 \times \text{Per capita Gross national income (GNI)}.$$

Canonical Set of the variables	Variables	Standardized Coefficient
Indicators of Environmental Measurement	Environmental Health	0.997
	Ecosystem Vitality	0.007
Human Development Indicators	Expected Years of Schooling	0.215
	Gross National Income	0.421
	Life Expectancy at Birth	0.383
	Mean Years of Schooling	0.083

Table- 6: Canonical coefficients in the composition of the variables

All of the coefficients in the canonical correlation model are positive and inclusive. Environmental Safety Nearing 0.997, it's over fourteen times higher than the ecological vitality rating of merely 0.007. The canonical variable of environmental performance is most heavily influenced by environmental health, making it the most relevant indication overall. Gross National Income (0.421) and Life Expectancy at Birth (0.383) were the two variables that had the greatest impact on human growth according to accepted standards. While the mean years of schooling had a very low coefficient of 0.083, the predicted years of schooling coefficient was 0.215, which was moderately contributing to HDI. The state of the environment is directly correlated with a country's classical human development score, which is calculated as a percentage of GDP.

Regardless, these representations were noteworthy because all of the coefficients were positive and there were substantial and credible correlations between human development and environmental performance. Based on the statistics given, the most important variable in HDI is the average number of years a person spends in education, while the most important variable in EPI is environmental health. Since a nation's environmental health is best measured by the average number of years its citizens spend in school, it stands to reason that more educated people tend to live in healthier environments. Unfortunately, the total HDI does not adequately reflect the economic component, or gross national income, so the correlation between economic performance and environmental performance is not as strong as it is for the other three HDIs.

Table 7 shows the canonical environmental performance explains within the variables of environmental performance metrics by 63.5% in each country. In addition, conventional human development is responsible for 86% of conventional

environmental performance, which equates to approximately 54.6% (i.e., $0.635 \times 0.8612 = 0.546$) of original environmental performance measures within the variables of Human Development metrics.

As the canonical human development indicators explain 79% of the variance in their own indicators, the canonical Human Development explains roughly 68% of the variance in the canonical environmental performance indicators (i.e., $0.79 \times 0.8612 = 0.68$). Therefore, from the vantage point of all countries, there is a medium-to-high explanatory potential between human development and environmental performance.

Figure-1: Canonical Correlation Analysis of Environmental Performance and Human Development

Performance of the Environmental explains by the original indicators standardized variances

Variables	Proportion of the Environmental performance	Canonical R-Square	Proportion of the Human Development
Environmental Performance	0.635	0.8612	0.546

The Human Development explains by the original indicators standardized variances

Variables	Proportion of the Human Development	Canonical R-Square	Proportion of the Environmental Performance
Measurement of the Human Development	0.79	0.8612	0.68

Table-7: Explanation of the Standardized variances of the variables (themselves and paired)

Canonical environmental performance (100%) and canonical human development (92.80%) have the strongest explanatory power for environmental health (Table 8), but only about 50% for ecosystem vitality. Among the two classical variables, life expectancy at birth has the strongest explanatory power (93.2% and 86.5%), followed by gross national income (91.6% and 85%), expected years of schooling (87.8% and 81.4%), and mean years of schooling (82.5% and 76.6%).

Canonical loading and Cross loading among the environmental indicators with the original variables set

Environmental performance Indicators	Canonical loading of the Environmental Performance	Canonical Cross loading of the Human Development
Environmental Health	1	0.928
Ecosystem Vitality	0.52	0.482

Canonical loading and Cross loading between the Human Development indicators with the canonical variables

Human Development Indicators	Canonical loading of the Human Development	Canonical loading of the Environmental Performance
Expected Years of Schooling	0.878	0.814
Gross National Income	0.916	0.85
Life Expectancy at Birth	0.932	0.865
Mean Years of Schooling	0.825	0.766

Table-8: Canonical loading and Cross loading among both sets indicators and the variables

Analysis and Result for South Asia Region: We have employed South Asian countries Canonical Correlation Analyses (CCA) between environmental performance indicators and human development indicators based on EPI-2022 and HDI-2022 report separately. Table-9 displays the results of the CCA for this region. The first set of computed canonical variate pairings has an eigenvalue of 7.759 with very strong canonical correlation coefficient of 0.941 and mutual explanatory power of 88.55%. The canonical correlation coefficient for the second set is 0.517, and the corresponding eigenvalue is 0.365. The eigenvalue of the first set of canonical variates is greater than 1 and can be anticipated; the second set of the variables eigenvalue is smaller than 1 and cannot be evaluated.

Canonical Correlation	R-Squared	Canonical Correlation	Null Hypothesis (H0)= Correlations the current and following rows are Zero (0).					
			EigenV alue	Wilks Statistic	F Value	Num DF	Den DF	Significance (P)
1	0.941	0.8855	7.759	0.084	1.229	8	4	0.45
2	0.517	0.2673	0.365	0.733	0.365	3	3	0.785

Table-9: Canonical Correlation Analysis for South Asia Region

The estimated canonical coefficients used to characterize the distribution of the canonical variables are shown in the Table-10. Measurement of the South Asia regional canonical variables of the first canonical variate pair can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Environmental Performance (South Asia)} = 0.914 \times \text{the Environmental Health} - 0.046 \times \text{the Ecosystem Vitality}.$$

Human development (South Asia) = $0.318 \times$ the Life expectancy at birth + $0.105 \times$ the Expected years of schooling + $(-0.203) \times$ the Mean years of schooling + $0.774 \times$ per capita Gross national income (GNI).

In the canonical correlation model, the coefficient is positive and inclusive for Environmental Health with a value closes to 0.914, but for Ecosystem Vitality it is negatively impacting Environmental Performance with a value of -0.046 in South Asia. Here, Environmental health is the most important indicator and has the highest contribution to t he composition of the canonical variable of environmental performance.

Canonical Set of the variables	Variables	Standardized Coefficient
Environmental Performance Indicators	Environmental Health	0.914
	Ecosystem Vitality	-0.046
Human Development Indicators	Expected Years of Schooling	0.105
	Gross National Income	0.774
	Life Expectancy at Birth	0.318
	Mean Years of Schooling	-0.203

Table-10: The Canonical coefficients in the composition of the variables in South Asia.

The highest contribution to canonical human development was made by Gross National Income (0.774) and Life Expectancy at Birth (0.318). The coefficient for expected years of schooling was moderately contributing to HDI (0.105), whereas the coefficient for mean years of schooling is negative (-0.203). A high canonical human development score, based on gross national income, is a direct cause of environmental performance in this region. The p-value of the first set is 0.45 and second set is 0.785, both of those are greater than 0.05; are not significant. Thus all the Null Hypothesis is accepted for the canonical correlation statistical analyses and has no explainable correlation between environmental performance and human development in South Asia region (Table-9).

Discussion of the findings

The optimum anticipated weights for indicators in the composite indices were calculated using canonical correlation analysis (CCA). CCA made an effort to connect human progress with environmental performance. When it comes to SDG-3, life expectancy at birth, and SDG-8.5, per capita gross national income, environmental health accounts for over 85% of the variation. In terms of Expected Years of Schooling (SDG-4.3), it has an influence of over 80%, whereas in terms of Mean Years of Schooling (SDG-4.4), it has an impact of less than 75%. While only 48.2% of the variance in ecosystem vitality can be explained by the normal Human Development Index, 92.8% of the variance in environmental health can be explained in this way. While Ecosystem Vitality only manages 52% in terms of environmental performance, Environmental Health manages 100%. Environmental success is a key driver of human advancement, according to a large body of research. They have a mutual explanatory power of 86% and a correlation of 92.8% in their standard composite indices. This study contributes to the achievement of SDG-2030 by providing empirical evidence of a strong and rational relationship between human development and environmental performance. Included for clarity are important discussions:

- (1) Environmental health and ecosystem vitality are marginally and favorably linked to environmental performance. This finding supports (Rapport 1998), (Jerry et al 2001), (Zhang et al 2006), and (Lai et al 2020)

that environmental performance measures are internally correlated, with a stronger correlation indicating a healthier environment. Environmental vitality comes from a healthy, functioning ecosystem. Ecosystem and environmental health are interdependent to protect human health and guarantee adequate environmental quality.

- (2) The four metrics of human progress (birth rate, anticipated years of schooling, mean years of education, and GNI) are moderately to strongly correlated. Noorbakhsh, F. (1998), found that HDI indicators are substantially connected, supporting by Booyesen, F. (2002) also. This suggests that progress in one area of human development will lead to progress in others, to various degrees. Education helps people find serenity and reach their potential, which advances society (Vander Zanden, J.W. 2006).
- (3) Environmental performance and human development have great explanatory power due to their interconnectedness (Qureshi, M.A. 2008). Knowledgeable people comprehend environmental health (Sakiko, F 2003); recognize the need of safeguarding their health, and take action. They also focus on environmental hygiene, minimizing environmental hazards, and limiting suspended particle exposure. All of the aforementioned suggest that environmental health can increase birth life expectancy (EPA, 2015).
- (4) The average and predicted schooling years are key indicators of human growth. EPI can assess the most essential link between environmental health's and projected schooling levels since HDI and EPI are highly connected. To better comprehend institutional settings for activities, responsibilities, and relations, policymakers should focus less on individual psychological outcomes and more on immediate environment structure (Lai et al 2020).
- (5) Promoting environmental health at all stages is crucial as it clearly correlates with life expectancy at birth (Gulis, G 2000). Life expectancy at birth, average schooling, and expected education affect ecological vitality (Faysissa et al 2008). Urbanization, income per capita, healthcare spending as a percentage of GDP, and worker carbon dioxide emissions also matter. Future sustainability management planning should embrace more effective ecological sustainability strategies for human growth.
- (6) The relationship between GNI and ecological vitality and health is weaker than the other three indicators of human progress. As development progresses, energy consumption and emissions rise (Panayotou, T. 1993). Industrial activity, automobile ownership, and electricity consumption are all linked to economic development and affluence (Sarkodie et al 2020). The necessity to provide people with modern renewable energy and/or industrialized technology to mitigate the trade-offs of economic development has major policy consequences (Cheng et al 2019).

Suggestions and Implications

The implications of the findings from the research on the relationship between environmental performance and human development are diverse and can inform policy-making, sustainability management, and development strategies.

- (1) **Interconnectedness of Environmental Health and Ecosystem Vitality:** The modest and positive association between environmental health and ecosystem vitality emphasizes the interconnected nature of these two components of environmental performance. Policymakers and environmental managers should recognize the importance of maintaining a balance between environmental health and ecosystem vitality for the overall well-being of both the environment and human society.

(2) **Interdependence of Human Development Indicators:** The strong relationships among human development indicators, such as birth rate, predicted years of schooling, mean years of education, and GDP, suggest that progress in one area can lead to progress in others. This underscores the holistic nature of human development and the need for integrated policies that address multiple aspects simultaneously.

(3) **Correlation between Environmental Performance and Human Development:** The strong correlation between individual measures of environmental performance and human development implies that improving environmental efficiency can positively impact human development. This highlights the importance of environmental policies in contributing to better access to education and resources, leading to improved health outcomes and increased life expectancy.

(4) **Focus on Mean and Expected Schooling Years:** The research underscores the significance of mean and expected schooling years as essential measures of human development with environmental health. It suggests that policymakers should prioritize environmental health in their policy agendas to enhance mean & expected schooling levels. This emphasis on the structure of the immediate environment over individual psychological outcomes can guide more effective policy interventions.

(5) **Promote Environmental Health for Life Expectancy:** The strong link between environmental health and life expectancy at birth emphasizes the vital relevance of promoting environmental health at all stages. Sustainability management planning should consider efficient methods of sustaining ecosystems to positively impact factors such as life expectancy, average schooling levels, and expected levels of education.

(6) **Association between GNI and Ecological Vitality:** While the association between Gross National Income (GNI) and ecological vitality is smaller compared to other human development indices, it still exists. This finding suggests that economic development can impact ecosystem, and policymakers should consider strategies to mitigate negative ecological effects associated with economic growth, such as pollution.

Conclusion

This research can assist policymakers attain the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for 2030 by highlighting the complicated relationship between environmental performance and human development. To ensure sustainability over the long run, it is necessary to strike a balance between environmental health, economic progress, and human well-being. This holistic approach recognizes the complexity of development and focuses on this need. Insights like this can inform the development of holistic strategies that boost both human and environmental health. It highlights how environmental performance and development are interdependent on human development indicators, ecosystem vitality, and environmental health. Measures of human development and environmental health that affect life expectancy, such as the mean and expected schooling years, highlight the necessity for comprehensive policymaking. There should be a balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability, and the correlation between GNI and ecological vitality addresses this, albeit to a lesser extent than other indicators. The necessity for sustainable practices to lessen the environmental impacts of economic expansion is reflected in policies that promote industrialized technology and renewable energy sources. To establish the impact of HDI on EPI or EPI on HDI, a longitudinal study may be necessary to establish the causal link between the two variables. In terms of human development and environmental efficiency, the results show that (1) expected and actual school years are not good indicators of future performance and (2) ecological vitality is not a good indicator of future performance. Policymakers can use this result as a framework for weighing the costs and benefits of various options when deciding how to balance economic growth with environmental quality. The research emphasizes the importance of laws that guarantee access to renewable energy

sources and industrialized technologies in order to reduce the negative impact on the environment caused by economic development.

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References

- [1] Onel, N., & Mukherjee, A. (2014). The effects of national culture and human development on environmental health. *Environment, development and sustainability*, 16, 79-101.
- [2] Wolfson, A., Ayalon, O., & Madar, D. (2020). National strategy for framing and prioritizing environmental protection research and development topics. *Sustainability*, 12(18), 7420.
- [3] Adil, A. A. (2018). Could human development be the key to environmental sustainability?. *Leonardo*, 51(2), 197-198.
- [4] Bojanic, D. (2011). Using a tourism importance–performance typology to investigate environmental sustainability on a global level. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(8), 989-1003.
- [5] Hsu, A., Johnson, L. A., & Lloyd, A. (2013). *Measuring progress: A practical guide from the developers of the environmental performance index (EPI)*. New Haven: Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy.
- [6] Popescu, G. H., Sima, V., Nica, E., & Gheorghe, I. G. (2017). Measuring sustainable competitiveness in contemporary economies—Insights from European economy. *Sustainability*, 9(7), 1230.
- [7] Liu, G., Brown, M. T., & Casazza, M. (2017). Enhancing the sustainability narrative through a deeper understanding of sustainable development indicators. *Sustainability*, 9(6), 1078.
- [8] Samuel, O. S., & Fayemi, A. K. (2019). Afro-communal virtue ethic as a foundation for environmental sustainability in Africa and beyond. *South African Journal of Philosophy*, 38(1), 79-95.
- [9] Cabello, J. M., Navarro-Jurado, E., Thiel-Ellul, D., Rodríguez-Díaz, B., & Ruiz, F. (2021). Assessing environmental sustainability by the double reference point methodology: the case of the provinces of Andalusia (Spain). *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 28(1), 4-17.
- [10] Jang, Y. J., & Zheng, T. (2020). Assessment of the environmental sustainability of restaurants in the US: The effects of restaurant characteristics on environmental sustainability performance. *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, 23(2), 133-148.
- [11] Opoku, D. G. J., Agyekum, K., & Ayarkwa, J. (2022). Drivers of environmental sustainability of construction projects: a thematic analysis of verbatim comments from built environment consultants. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(6), 1033-1041.
- [12] Esty, D. C., & Emerson, J. W. (2018). From crises and gurus to science and metrics: Yale's Environmental Performance Index and the rise of data-driven policymaking. In *Routledge Handbook of Sustainability Indicators* (pp. 93-102). Routledge.
- [13] Lai, S. L., & Chen, D. N. (2020). A research on the relationship between environmental sustainability management and human development. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9001.

- [14] Emerson, J. W., Hsu, A., Levy, M. A., de Sherbinin, A., Mara, V., Esty, D. C., & Jaiteh, M. (2012). Environmental performance index and pilot trend environmental performance index. New Haven: Yale Center for Environmental Law and Policy.
- [15] Zhang, Y., Yang, Z., & Yu, X. (2006). Measurement and evaluation of interactions in complex urban ecosystem. *Ecological Modelling*, 196(1-2), 77-89.
- [16] Qasim, A. W. (2013). United Nations development programme (UNDP). Human development report 2013. *Pakistan Development Review*, 52(1), 95-96.
- [17] Ul Haq, M. (1995). Reflections on human development. oxford university Press.
- [18] Guo, M., Nowakowska-Grunt, J., Gorbanyov, V., & Egorova, M. (2020). Green technology and sustainable development: Assessment and green growth frameworks. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6571.
- [19] Panayotou, T. (1993). Empirical tests and policy analysis of environmental degradation at different stages of economic development.
- [20] Gallego-Álvarez, I., Vicente-Galindo, M. P., Galindo-Villardón, M. P., & Rodríguez-Rosa, M. (2014). Environmental performance in countries worldwide: Determinant factors and multivariate analysis. *Sustainability*, 6(11), 7807-7832.
- [21] Orlitzky, M., Siegel, D. S., & Waldman, D. A. (2011). Strategic corporate social responsibility and environmental sustainability. *Business & Society*, 50(1), 6-27.
- [22] Esty, D. C., Levy, M., Srebotnjak, T., & De Sherbinin, A. (2005). Environmental sustainability index: benchmarking national environmental stewardship. New Haven: Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy, 47, 60.
- [23] Hsu, A., Johnson, L. A., & Lloyd, A. (2013). Measuring progress: A practical guide from the developers of the environmental performance index (EPI). New Haven: Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy.
- [24] Popescu, G. H., Sima, V., Nica, E., & Gheorghe, I. G. (2017). Measuring sustainable competitiveness in contemporary economies – Insights from European economy. *Sustainability*, 9(7), 1230.
- [25] Cheng, R., & Li, W. (2019). Evaluating environmental sustainability of an urban industrial plan under the three-line environmental governance policy in China. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 251, 109545.
- [26] Zuo, X., Hua, H., Dong, Z., & Hao, C. (2017). Environmental performance index at the provincial level for China 2006–2011. *Ecological Indicators*, 75, 48-56.
- [27] Glatzer, W. (2011). Cross-national comparisons of quality of life in developed nations, including the impact of globalization. In *Handbook of social indicators and quality of life research* (pp. 381-398).

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